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Influence Of Information Services On The Spread Of HIV In Makurdi, Benue State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of information services on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. Four research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of all Senior Secondary School students in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. The HIV/AIDS Information Services Questionnaire (HIV/AIDSISQ) was developed by the researcher and administered to gather data. The questionnaire was made up of 4 sections and 5 items under each section giving a total of 20 items. The 4 sections provided statements to answer the 4 research questions developed to guide the study. Respondents indicated their agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the two options of “Yes” or “No”. The options had numerical values of 2 and 1 respectively. The data collected through questionnaires were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. Frequencies and percentages were used to answer research questions while the chi-square (χ^2) of goodness of fit was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at a P-Value of 0.000. The findings of the study were as follows; Community mobilization has significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State; Peer education has significant influence on the spread of HIV; Mass media has significant influence on the spread of HIV; and General advocacy has significant influence on the spread of HIV. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made among others; Governmental and non-governmental organisations should foster community engagement by supporting grassroots organizations and initiatives focused on HIV prevention. These organisations should encourage local communities to take an active role in organizing events, workshops, and support groups that address HIV-related issues.

Keywords: HIV, AIDS, Information services.

INTRODUCTION

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is an infection that attacks the body’s immune system. Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) is the most advanced stage of the disease. HIV targets the body’s white blood cells, weakening the immune system. This makes it easier to get sick with diseases like tuberculosis, infections and some cancers. HIV is spread from the body fluids of an infected person, including blood, breast milk, semen and vaginal fluids. It is not spread by kisses, hugs or sharing food. It can also spread from a mother to her baby.

Nigeria ranks third among countries with highest burden of Human Immuno-Deficiency Virus (HIV) infection in the world. The 2019 Nigeria National HIV/AIDS Indicator and Impact Survey found that 1.9 million people are living with HIV and AIDS in Nigeria as at 2018 (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2023). There is varied geographical HIV prevalence in Nigeria. The progress made is inequitable across geographical locations and sub-populations. Benue state has the second highest HIV prevalence in Nigeria. Agegnehu and Tesema (2020) posit that, globally, and particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), Human Immunodeficiency Virus /Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (HIV/AIDS) was the leading cause of morbidity and mortality among reproductive-age women. In sub-Saharan Africa, it is estimated that 60% of HIV/AIDS patients were reproductive-age women however, less than 30% of reproductive-age women have comprehensive knowledge of HIV/AIDS. This lack of knowledge about the disease makes its propagation to fester especially amongst the illiterates. However, countries all over been making deliberate efforts to ensure that information about HIV/AIDS is spread to the nooks and crannies of the society. Various means have been utilized in the process of information dissemination. Some of such measures have been through community mobilization (or participation), mass media, peer education, among others including general advocacy and specialized seminars and workshops.

According to Mbuagbaw and Shurik (2014), since the advent of the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) there have been considerable challenges to health systems throughout the world. Many countries have developed measures to combat the spread of the virus and the trends are improving, mostly due to the introduction of potent new combinations of medications, the development of effective prevention strategies and increased community awareness. These improvements would not have been possible without the mobilisation of communities around the world, who, recognising their vulnerability, have taken collective action to curb the propagation of HIV (Mbuagbaw & Shurik, 2014). Community involvement is a vital precondition for effective HIV/AIDS management. It plays an important role in enabling health-related behaviours and reducing HIV-transmission, and in the reduction of stigma. It is also vital for facilitating timely and appropriate accessing of health and welfare services where these exist, and for supporting optimal treatment adherence (Skovdal, Campbell, Nhongo, Nyamukapa & Gregson, 2011).

Aside community mobilization, peer groups can be utilized in the dissemination of information about HIV, this is done through peer education and support. According to Visser (2014) peer education and support involves the training and use of individuals from the target group to educate and support their peers. Peer-led interventions are based on the assumption that behaviour is socially influenced and that behavioural norms are developed through interaction. They are also derived from the extensive literature on the value of social support and non-professional help in promoting mental health (Visser, 2014). Peer education and support can be especially effective among adolescents because friends are their main sources of information about sexual practices, and peer influence often motivates their behaviour.

Peer education typically involves the use of members of a given group to effect change among other members of the same group. Peer education is often used to effect change at the individual level by attempting to modify a person's knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, or behaviours. However, peer education may also effect change at the group or societal level by modifying norms and stimulating collective action that leads to changes in programs and policies (Visser, 2014).

The utilization of mass media as a channel for the communication and dissemination of HIV/AIDS information has been a very effective tool for HIV/AIDS awareness campaigns in recent years. The progress made in programmes designed to raise this understanding has been quite remarkable, and mass media remains the most practical means of conveyance of accurate knowledge about HIV/AIDS, given the high level of public accessibility to various forms of media, particularly television and internet. Employing mass media as the primary resource for the propagation of the HIV/AIDS youth awareness campaign, in particular, has proved to be of inestimable value, for mass media plays a crucial role in raising public awareness of the dangers of the pandemic and in eliminating stigma and discrimination of PWHAs (Smoot, 2009).

Mass media encompasses the radio, television, print-media, billboards and the world-wide web forms of communications. The mass media can be relied upon as a potent force for achieving attitude and behaviour change in society. The mass media which includes the print media (press) and the electronic media (broadcast) represents a crucial resource as well as a formidable platform for propagating and inculcating the values inherent in every culture and people. The mass media is used to inform and educate the members of any given society (Odigbo, Ugwu & Ekemezie, 2017).

General advocacy involves active support for the spread of information about HIV/AIDS, provision of social facilities, free testing and contraceptives to help curtail the spread of the virus and also demanding that governments and organizations make deliberate efforts to curb the disease. Sunguya, Munisamy, Pongpanich, Yasuoka and Jimba (2016) in a study observed that HIV advocacy programmes are partly responsible for the global community's success in reducing the burden of HIV. They maintain that, in the era of antiretroviral therapy, advocacy programmes have contributed a great deal to control HIV infection. It is of this view that the researcher deems it fit to investigate the influence of information services on the prevention of spread of HIV/AIDS in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

Everywhere volunteer HIV testing is been carried out in town one is likely to see a lot of people queuing up to be tested. Yet many leave such mobile testing centres to indulge in unprotected sexual intercourse, and use sharp objects with other people. This is the consequence of a lack of deliberate effort to prevent the spread of the disease. This could either be because of lack of information out there, or the general public is just not bothered about the spread of the virus. However, the disease has been responsible for a lot of deaths, and the consequences range from psychological, physical and socioeconomic. In the current study, the researcher aims find out the potency of different information services on the spread of the virus. In doing this, the researcher shall also seek to find out the level of information about HIV among the population in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. The target population is adolescents in senior secondary schools. This set of youths is targeted because they are still very young and at the stage where they like exploring and trying out new things, including sexual intercourse. The researcher shall assess their level of information about HIV/AIDS, sources of information and also provide safety measures for the prevention of the virus.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the influence of community mobilization on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State?
2. What is the influence of peer education on the spread of HIV?
3. What is the influence of mass media on the spread of HIV?
4. What is the influence of general advocacy on the spread of HIV?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 confidence level of significance:

1. Community mobilization has no significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.
2. Peer education has no significant influence on the spread of HIV.
3. Mass media has no significant influence on the spread of HIV.
4. General advocacy has no significant influence on the spread of HIV.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the analytical survey research design. The population comprised of all youths in Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. A sample size of 400 was drawn out randomly using the Taro Yamane Formula for selecting sample size. The HIV/AIDS Information Services Questionnaire (HIV/AIDSISQ) was administered to gather data. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, while the Chi-square goodness of fit test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, a reliability test was

conducted on 50 teachers whom were not part of the sample of the main study. Data were collated and analysed for reliability using Cronbach Alpha correlation co-efficient. The reliability co-efficient of .928 was realized.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question 1

What is the influence of community mobilization on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State?

Table 1: Analysis of influence of community mobilization on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

S/N	Item	Responses and Frequencies	
		Yes (%)	No (%)
1	I have witnessed a HIV/AIDS activity in my community.	271 (67.8)	129 (32.2)
2	HIV testing is occasionally done in my community.	396 (99.0)	4 (1.0)
3	I have been part of a HIV volunteer activity in my community.	341 (85.3)	59 (14.8)
4	An NGO has come to my community to give us information about HIV.	234 (58.5)	166 (41.5)
5	Some people in my locality have volunteered to help NGOs carry out some activities about HIV.	316 (79.0)	84 (21.0)

Data in table 1 shows the frequency distribution for the influence of community mobilization on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State and their corresponding percentages. Generally, the responses are spread out across both options of “Yes” and “No” but a majority of the respondents affirmed to the influence of community mobilization on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Research Question 2

What is the influence of peer education on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State?

Table 2: Analysis of influence of peer education on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

S/N	Item	Responses and Frequencies	
		Yes (%)	No (%)
6	I have heard about HIV from my friends.	342 (85.5)	58 (14.5)
7	One of my friends has had sex with a condom.	322 (80.5)	78 (19.5)
8	I have told my friends about HIV and how it is contracted.	338 (84.5)	62 (15.5)
9	I don't want to indulge in premarital sex like some of my peers.	330 (82.5)	70 (17.5)
10	My friends and I know that HIV can be contracted through sharing of sharp objects.	298 (74.5)	102 (25.5)

Data in table 2 shows the frequency distribution for the influence of peer education on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State and their corresponding percentages. Generally, the responses are spread out across both options of “Yes” and “No” but a majority of the respondents

affirmed to the influence of peer education on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Research Question 3

What is the influence of mass media on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State?

Table 3: Analysis of influence of mass media on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

S/N	Item	Responses and Frequencies	
		Yes (%)	No (%)
11	I have heard of HIV on the radio and television.	322 (80.5)	78 (19.5)
12	I have watched the symptoms of HIV on the television.	352 (88.0)	48 (12.0)
13	I have watched a HIV programme on the television.	250 (62.5)	150 (37.5)
14	I know some ways of preventing HIV because I heard them on the radio some time ago.	309 (77.3)	91 (22.8)
15	I have seen posts about HIV on social media platforms.	382 (95.5)	18 (4.5)

Data in table 3 shows the frequency distribution for the influence of mass media on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State and their corresponding percentages. Generally, the responses are spread out across both options of “Yes” and “No” but a majority of the respondents affirmed to the influence of mass media on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Research Question 4

What is the influence of general advocacy on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State?

Table 4: Analysis of influence of general advocacy on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

S/N	Item	Responses and Frequencies	
		Yes (%)	No (%)
16	I have witnessed a campaign about HIV in my community.	322 (80.5)	78 (19.5)
17	World AIDS day was celebrated by some people in my locality.	303 (75.8)	97 (24.2)
18	There have been activities about HIV in my community where we were taught how to use a condom.	251 (62.7)	149 (37.3)
19	Some NGOs come to my locality to talk about the dangers of HIV and its prevention.	327 (81.8)	73 (18.2)
20	I have heard someone speak about how the government can solve the problem of HIV.	307 (76.8)	93 (23.3)

Data in table 4 shows the frequency distribution for the influence of general advocacy on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State and their corresponding percentages. Generally, the responses are spread out across both options of “Yes” and “No” but a majority of the respondents affirmed to the influence of general advocacy on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

4.2.2 Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (X^2) was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Community mobilization has no significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Table 5: Chi-square Test of influence of community mobilization on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
Yes	271	200.0	1	.05	50.410	.000	Sig.
No	129	200.0					
Total	400						

Table 5 revealed that $\chi^2 = 50.410$, $df = 1$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 1 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that community mobilization has no significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State is rejected. This implies that community mobilization has significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Hypothesis 2

Peer education has no significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Table 6: Chi-square Test of influence of peer education on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
Yes	342	200.0	1	.05	201.640	.000	Sig.
No	58	200.0					
Total	400						

Table 6 revealed that $\chi^2 = 201.640$, $df = 1$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 1 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that peer education has no significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State is rejected. This implies that peer education has significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Hypothesis 3

Mass media has no significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Table 7: Chi-square Test of influence of mass media on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
Yes	322	200.0	1	.05	148.840	.000	Sig.
No	78	200.0					
Total	400						

Table 7 revealed that $\chi^2 = 148.840$, $df = 1$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 1 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that mass media has no significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State is rejected. This implies that mass media has significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Hypothesis 4

General advocacy has no significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Table 8: Chi-square Test of influence of general advocacy on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
Yes	322	200.0	1	.05	148.840	.000	Sig.
No	78	200.0					
Total	400						

Table 8 revealed that $\chi^2 = 148.840$, $df = 1$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 1 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that general advocacy has no significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State is rejected. This implies that general advocacy has significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research is organized around the research questions and hypotheses for ease of reading and comprehension. The four null hypotheses that were postulated and tested were all rejected.

The first finding of the study revealed that community mobilization has significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. This implies that the assemblage and utilization of community members and community resources in the dissemination of information about HIV/AIDS and probable ways of curtailing and curbing the disease effective in controlling the propagation of the virus. The collected data indicates that more than 50% of the respondents agreed to having witness a community activity geared towards awareness creation and the control of HIV/AIDS. The respondents also affirmed that community involvement in activities for HIV/AIDS prevention was efficient in curtailing the virus. Similarly, Kumnah (2016) found in a study in Plateau State that involvement of communities in in the different senatorial districts of the state in the of HIV/AIDS activities was significant in the control and management of HIV/AIDS in the implementation of national reproductive health plan in the State. Moreso, Okonkwoh (2010) also found in a study that community involvement did not only influence awareness but response to treatment and also greatly contributed to reducing mother-child transmission. The efficiency of the strategy led the researcher to conclude that involving community members in mother to child transmission of HIV/AIDS is an excellent approach to breaking down barriers that influence HIV transmission from mother to child.

The second finding of the study revealed that peer education has significant influence on the spread of HIV. This finding implies that the use of members of a given group to spread information about HIV/AIDS is a potent way of curtailing the spread of the virus. As the name implies, peers are people with shared interests therefore, such persons are spotted and given information about HIV so that they can share with their other peers. Peers who are also considered friends are utilized in peer education in the dissemination of information about HIV/AIDS to their peer groups. This finding is similar to that of Visser (2014) whom found in a study that peer education can contribute to the delayed onset of sexual activity, and can therefore contribute to the prevention of HIV/AIDS amongst adolescents. Similarly, Hassan *et al.*, (2014) also found that adolescents that underwent peer education programme reported superior knowledge on HIV/AIDS than their counterparts who did not. Also, such adolescents reported fewer numbers of multiple sexual partners (9.7%) compared to those in the comparison sites that did not receive peer education and training.

The third finding of the study revealed that mass media has significant influence on the spread of HIV. This finding implies that the utilization of radio, television, newspapers, and other print and non-print resources including the internet and social media platforms to disseminate information about HIV is an effective strategy for curbing and curtailing the spread of HIV/AIDS in Makurdi, Benue State. With the explosion of mass and social media, a lot of young and old people can easily get access to information not just about HIV but also about many other issues. However, in the activities of HIV/AIDS, mass media was found to be very potent in creating awareness about the virus and also about its preventive measures.

In a similar vein, Odigbo, Ugwu and Ekemezie (2017) in a study found that the applications of social marketing tools via the mass media have significant positive effect on the prevention of HIV/AIDS in Nigeria. It is worthy of note that the researchers were also concerned about the potency of African traditional media, thereby also finding it relevant in curtailing the virus. The researchers therefore concluded that a combination of the mass media and Africa traditional media are needed as social marketing tools and strategies for achieving successful HIV/AIDS prevention campaigns in developing countries like Nigeria. Muktar (2018) corroborates their position as he also found in a study that mass media messages contributed positively to the reduction of the virus in Kano and recommended that more programmes on health and HIV/AIDS be aired in the media.

The fourth finding of the study revealed that general advocacy has significant influence on the spread of HIV. This finding implies that active support for the spread of information about HIV/AIDS, provision of social facilities, free testing and contraceptives to help curtail the spread of the virus and also demanding that governments and organizations make deliberate efforts to curb the disease all culminate to influence the spread of the virus. More than 50% of the respondents affirmed to having witness a community outreach and a general advocacy programme carried out in their locality in the past. Similarly, Sunguya *et al.*, (2016) found in a study that following the implementation of HIV advocacy programs, participants reported improved information-seeking behaviour, as well as a notable increase in knowledge. General advocacy programmes have been found to be efficient strategies in curtailing the virus. Moreso, Peltzer *et al.*, (2012) found in an experimental study that advocacy interventions decreased unprotected sexual contact in South Africa. Multiple sexual partnerships and the number of sexual encounters also decreased following implementation of HIV advocacy programmes. These results affirm those of the current study.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that information services have significant influence on the spread of HIV in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. The findings of the study underscore the pivotal role of information services, including advocacy campaigns, peer education, community mobilization, and mass media, in shaping the trajectory of HIV spread. These channels serve as powerful tools for disseminating accurate information, raising awareness, and promoting preventive behaviours among communities. By leveraging these platforms effectively, stakeholders can actively engage and empower individuals to make informed decisions regarding their sexual health, ultimately contributing to the containment of HIV transmission.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Governmental and non-governmental organisations should foster community engagement by supporting grassroots organizations and initiatives focused on HIV prevention. These organisations should encourage local communities to take an active role in organizing events, workshops, and support groups that address HIV-related issues.
2. Individuals, governments and organisations should develop and implement peer education programmes that target high-risk populations and communities. Peer educators should be trained to effectively communicate information about HIV prevention, testing, and treatment to their peers.
3. There should be increase in funding and support for mass media campaigns that focus on HIV prevention, awareness, and education. Also, there should be collaboration between media outlets to disseminate accurate and up-to-date information about HIV through television, radio, newspapers, and online platforms.
4. Government and the general public should support organizations that advocate for policies promoting safe sex, access to healthcare, and non-discriminatory practices for individuals living with HIV.

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